

Original Article

Publication History:

Published 21/12/2020

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4392804

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Najam-ul-Sehar Javed,
DHQ Hospital Jhelum
najamjaved25@gmail.com

Cite this article as:

Yousaf Z, Walayat F, Jave
NUS. Prevalence of asthma
among medical students.
Int. J. Med. Dent. Allied
Health Sci. 2020;2(12). 622-
26

© Copyright 2020

This is an open access article
distributed under the terms of the
Creative Commons Attribution
License CC-BY 4.0., which
permits unrestricted use,
distribution, and reproduction in
any medium, provided the
original author and source are
credited.

**PREVALENCE OF NEEDLESTICK
INJURIES AMONG HEALTH
PROFESSIONALS**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. ZEESHAN YOUSAF, LAHORE MEDICAL AND DENTAL COLLEGE LAHORE
2. DR. FARHAN WALAYAT, PAKISTAN INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES ISLAMABAD
3. DR. NAJAM-UL-SEHAR JAVED, DHQ HOSPITAL JHELUM

ABSTRACT:

Needlestick injury is the penetration of the skin by a hypodermic needle or other sharp object that has been in contact with blood, tissue or other body fluids before the exposure. Even though the acute physiological effects of a needlestick injury are generally negligible, these injuries can lead to transmission of blood-borne diseases. This cross-sectional study was conducted among health professionals of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, designation and history of needlestick injuries were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 70 health professionals included in this study. There were 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the health professionals was 27.23 ± 2.34 years. There were 45 doctors, 15 nurses and 10 technicians in this study. Out of 70 professionals, 23 had experienced occasional needlestick injury during different procedures.

KEYWORD: NEEDLESTICK INJURIES

INTRODUCTION:

Needlestick injury is the penetration of the skin by a hypodermic needle or other sharp object that has been in contact with blood, tissue or other body fluids before the exposure. Even though the acute physiological effects of a needlestick injury are generally negligible, these injuries can lead to transmission of blood-borne diseases, placing those exposed at increased risk of infection from disease causing pathogens, such as the hepatitis B virus (HBV), hepatitis C virus (HCV), and human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Among healthcare workers and laboratory personnel worldwide, more than 25 blood-borne virus infections have been reported to have been caused by needlestick injuries. In addition to needlestick injuries, transmission of these viruses can also occur as a result of contamination of the mucous membranes, such as those of the eyes, with blood or body fluids, but needlestick injuries make up more than 80% of all percutaneous exposure incidents in the United

States. Various other occupations are also at increased risk of needlestick injury, including law enforcement, laborers, tattoo artists, food preparers, and agricultural workers.

Needlestick injuries occur in the healthcare environment. When drawing blood, administering an intramuscular or intravenous drug, or performing any procedure involving sharps, accidents can occur and facilitate the transmission of blood-borne diseases. Injuries also commonly occur during needle recapping or via improper disposal of devices into an overfilled or poorly located sharps container. Lack of access to appropriate personal protective equipment, or alternatively, employee failure to use provided equipment, increases the risk of occupational needlestick injuries. Needlestick injuries may also occur when needles are exchanged between personnel, loaded into a needle driver, or when sutures are tied off while still connected to the needle. Needlestick injuries are more common during night shifts

and for less experienced people; fatigue, high workload, shift work, high pressure, or high perception of risk can all increase the chances of a needlestick injury. During surgery, a surgical needle or other sharp instrument may inadvertently penetrate the glove and skin of operating room personnel; scalpel injuries tend to be larger than a needlestick. Generally, needlestick injuries cause only minor visible trauma or bleeding; however, even in the absence of bleeding the risk of viral infection remains (1-3). The objective of this study was to see the prevalence of needlestick injuries among health professionals.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among health professionals of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, designation and history of needlestick injuries were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were

presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 70 health professionals included in this study. There were 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the health professionals was 27.23 ± 2.34 years. There were 45 doctors, 15 nurses and 10 technicians in this study. Out of 70 professionals, 23 had experienced occasional needlestick injury during different procedures.

DISCUSSION:

In 2007, the World Health Organization estimated annual global needlestick injuries at 2 million per year, and another investigation estimated 3.5 million injuries yearly. The European Biosafety Network estimated 1 million needlestick injuries annually in Europe. The US Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) estimates 5.6 million workers in the

healthcare industry are at risk of occupational exposure to blood-borne diseases via percutaneous injury. The US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimates more than 600,000 needlestick injuries occur among healthcare workers in the US annually.

Among healthcare workers, nurses and physicians appear especially at risk; those who work in an operating room environment are at the highest risk. An investigation among American surgeons indicates that almost every surgeon experienced at least one such injury during their training. More than half of needlestick injuries that occur during surgery happen while surgeons are sewing the muscle or fascia. Within the medical field, specialties differ in regard to the risk of needlestick injury: surgery, anesthesia, otorhinolaryngology (ENT), internal medicine, and dermatology have high risk, whereas radiology and pediatrics have relatively low rates of injury. A systematic review of 45 studies of sharps injuries in surgical staff

found that sharps injuries occur once in 10 operations per staff member. Per 100 person-years, the injury rate in surgical staff was 88.2 (95% CI, 61.3-126.9; 21 studies) for self-reported injuries, 40.0 for perforations (95% CI, 19.2-83.5; 15 studies), and 5.8 for administrative injuries (95% CI, 2.7-12.2; 5 studies). Self-report probably overestimates the real risk and administrative data underestimate the risk considerably. Perforation data are probably the most valid indicators. Considering that the perforation rates provided here are much lower than the self-reported injuries used to calculate the burden of disease due to sharps injuries by the WHO, these calculations should be revised.

In the United States, approximately half of all needlestick injuries affecting health care workers are not reported, citing the long reporting process and its interference with work as their reason for not reporting an incident. The availability of hotlines, witnesses, and response

teams can increase the percentage of reports (4-6).

REFERENCES:

1. Lavoie, M; Verbeek, JH; Pahwa, M (2014). "Devices for preventing percutaneous exposure injuries caused by needles in healthcare personnel". The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. 3 (3. Art. No.: CD009740): CD009740. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD009740.pub2. PMID 24610008.
2. Mast EE, Weinbaum CM, Fiore AE, Alter MJ, Bell BP, Finelli L, Rodewald LE, Douglas JM, Janssen RS, Ward JW (2006). "A comprehensive immunization strategy to eliminate transmission of hepatitis B virus infection in the United States: recommendations of the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP). Part II: Immunization of adults". MMWR. CDC. 55 (RR-16): 1-33, quiz CE1-4. PMID 17159833.
3. Wodak, A; Cooney, A (2006). "Do needle syringe programs reduce HIV infection among injecting drug users: A comprehensive review of

the international evidence". *Subst Use Misuse*. 41 (6-7): 777-813. doi:10.1080/10826080600669579. PMID 16809167.

4. Jones, L; Pickering, L; Sumnall, H; McVeigh, J; Bellis, MA (2010). "Optimal provision of needle and syringe programmes for injecting drug users: A systematic review". *International Journal of Drug Policy*. 21 (5): 335-42. doi:10.1016/j.drugpo.2010.02.001 . PMID 20189375.

5. Abdul-Quader, AS; Feelemyer, J; Modi, S; Stein, ES; Briceno, A; Semaan, S; Horvath, T; Kennedy, GE; Des Jarlais, DC (2013). "Effectiveness of structural-level needle/syringe programs to reduce HCV and HIV infection among people who inject drugs: A systematic review". *AIDS and Behavior*. 17 (9): 2878-92. doi:10.1007/s10461-013-0593-y. PMC 6509353. PMID 23975473.

6. Verbeek, Jos (2018). "Incidence of sharps injuries in surgical units, a meta-analysis and meta-regression". *American Journal of Infection Control*. 47 (4): 448-455. doi:10.1016/j.ajic.2018.10.003.